

Evaluation of CMIP5 EURO-CORDEX: Minimum daily 2 m temperature

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References

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Heatmap: Difference from observations

Regional average of the difference in 2 m daily minimal temperature (°C) between model simulations and observational estimates in different seasons (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, Annual) in the reference period 1991–2020. Regions are Europe, West West-Central Europe (WWCE), PRUDENCE Alps (Alps), and Switzerland (CH). Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v19.0eHOM until December 2018 combined with v27.0 thereafter - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Maps: Annual mean difference from observations over Europe

Annual mean differences in 2 m daily minimal temperature (°C) between model simulations and gridded observational estimates in the reference period 1991-2020 displayed as maps for each model simulation. Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v19.0eHOM until December 2018 combined with v27.0 thereafter - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Heatmap: RMSE by season and region

Root-mean-squared-error (RMSE) in 2 m daily minimal temperature for each model simulation compared to observational estimates in different seasons (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, Annual) in the reference period 1991-2020. Regions are Europe, West West-Central Europe (WWCE), PRUDENCE Alps (Alps), and Switzerland (CH). Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v19.0eHOM until December 2018 combined with v27.0 thereafter - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Heatmap: Historical linear trend

Regional historical (1971-2020) linear trend in 2 m daily minimal temperature as °C/decade in each model simulation in different seasons (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, Annual). The linear trend is estimated as least squares polynomial fit of degree 1. Regions are Europe, West West-Central Europe (WWCE), PRUDENCE Alps (Alps), and Switzerland (CH).

Maps: Historical linear trend of annual mean over Alps

Annual historical (1971-2020) linear trend in 2 m daily minimal temperature as °C/decade in each model simulation displayed as maps over the PRUDENCE Alps region.

tasmin Annual trend 1971-2020 [°C / decade]

Heatmap: Historical linear trend difference from observations

Regional average difference in historical (1971-2020) trend between model simulation and observational estimates in different seasons (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, Annual). Regions are Europe, West West-Central Europe (WWCE), PRUDENCE Alps (Alps), and Switzerland (CH). Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v19.0eHOM until December 2018 combined with v27.0 thereafter - embedded with MeteSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Maps: Historical linear trend difference from observations of annual mean over Alps

Annual historical (1971-2020) trend difference in 2 m daily minimal temperature as °C/decade between model simulation and observational estimates displayed as maps over the PRUDENCE Alps region. Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v19.0eHOM until December 2018 combined with v27.0 thereafter - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

tasmin Annual trend bias from observations 1971-2020 [°C / decade]

Heatmap: Change in mean values between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099

Regional average change in 2 m daily minimal temperature (°C) from 1991-2020 to 2070-2099 in different seasons (DJF, MAM, JJA, SON, Annual). Regions are Europe, West West-Central Europe (WWCE), PRUDENCE Alps (Alps), and Switzerland (CH).

Maps: Change in annual mean between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099

Change in annual mean 2 m daily minimal temperature (°C) from 1991-2020 to 2070-2099 displayed as maps over the PRUDENCE Alps region.

tasmin change 2070-2099 - 1991-2020 [°C]

Timeseries: Annual mean 1971-2099, grouped by GCM

Annual mean timeseries from 1971-2099 in 2 m daily minimal temperature in Europe and Switzerland (CH) for each model simulation, grouped by driving GCM. Observational estimates from EOBS on EUR-11 - v19.0eHOM until December 2018 combined with v27.0 thereafter - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland are displayed in black. The effective Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS; °C) for each GCM is displayed in the upper left corner of each figure.

- Model
- CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1
 - GERICS-REMO2015_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - ICTP-RegCM4-6_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - IPSL-WRF381P_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1
 - MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r12i1p1
 - SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - SMHI-RCA4_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r3i1p1
 - UHOH-WRF361H_ICHEC-EC-EARTH_r1i1p1
 - Observations

- Model
- CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - CNRM-ALADIN63_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - GERICS-REMO2015_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - ICTP-RegCM4-6_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - SMHI-RCA4_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - UHOH-WRF361H_MOHC-HadGEM2-ES_r1i1p1
 - Observations

- Model
- CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - CNRM-ALADIN63_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - DMI-HIRHAM5_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - GERICS-REMO2015_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - ICTP-RegCM4-6_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - IPSL-WRF381P_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - KNMI-RACMO22E_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05_CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5_r1i1p1
 - Observations

Appendices

Taylor Diagrams

Taylor Diagrams showing RMSE, correlation, and standard deviation in one diagram for all model simulations for 2 m daily minimal temperature and observational estimates (black star and dashed line) for Europe and Switzerland during the period 1991-2020. Standard deviation is proportional to the radial distance from the origin, correlation is related to the azimuthal angle, and RMSE is proportional to the distance from the observations (grey contours). Observational estimates given by EOBS on EUR-11 - v19.0eHOM until December 2018 combined with v27.0 thereafter - embedded with MeteoSwiss gridded data over Switzerland

Maps: Seasonal mean difference from observations over Europe

Maps: Historical linear trend of seasonal mean over Alps

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r2i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CanESM2 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MIROC5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P EC-EARTH r12i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P NorESM1-M r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r12i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r3i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

Maps: Historical linear trend difference from observations of seasonal mean over Alps

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r2i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CanESM2 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MIROC5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P EC-EARTH r12i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P NorESM1-M r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r12i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r3i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H EC-EARTH r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

Maps: Change in seasonal mean between 1991-2020 and 2070-2099

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17 CanESM2 r1i1p1

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17 MIROC5 r1i1p1

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

CLMcom-CCLM4-8-17 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

CLMcom-ETH-COSMO-crCLIM-v1-1 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

CNRM-ALADIN63 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

DMI-HIRHAM5 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CanESM2 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MIROC5 r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

GERICS-REMO2015 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

ICTP-RegCM4-6 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P EC-EARTH r12i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

IPSL-WRF381P NorESM1-M r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r12i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E EC-EARTH r3i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

KNMI-RACMO22E NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 CNRM-CM5 r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MOHC-HadREM3-GA7-05 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

MPI-CSC-REMO2009 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r12i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 EC-EARTH r3i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 IPSL-CM5A-MR r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r2i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 MPI-ESM-LR r3i1p1

SMHI-RCA4 NorESM1-M r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H EC-EARTH r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H HadGEM2-ES r1i1p1

UHOH-WRF361H MPI-ESM-LR r1i1p1

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